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EQUITY, SUSTAINABILITY, AND THE PARTICIPATION OF THE GLOBAL SOUTH IN SPACE GOVERNANCE

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ABSTRACT

The search for effective ways to ensure the safety and long-term use of outer space has become a central challenge for space law globally. In this context, sustainability is widely regarded as essential to maintaining continued access to outer space while ensuring that the benefits derived from space activities are shared among all countries and across generations. Nevertheless, the rapid expansion of space activities and the growing space industry have exposed critical gaps in global governance, particularly concerning unequal participation in shaping the legal frameworks that will determine the future of humanity in space. This paper examines contemporary space governance frameworks – both binding and non-binding – and their relationship with the principles of equity and sustainability. It argues that, while these mechanisms may address sustainability-related challenges, they risk reinforcing structural asymmetries between established spacefaring nations and countries with emerging or limited space capabilities unless equity is incorporated as an operative principle in decision-making processes. In this sense, the article explores how integrating equity into global space governance may contribute to fairer participation and to the long-term sustainability of outer space activities. By examining the interaction between legal structures, international cooperation, and sustainability-oriented instruments, the article identifies structural barriers embedded in current governance arrangements. Rather than proposing an exhaustive reform agenda, the study clarifies how equity and sustainability intersect in contemporary space governance and contributes to ongoing discussions on the more inclusive participation of Global South countries in shaping legal norms governing the sustainable use of outer space.

KEYWORDS: Space Governance; Sustainability; Equity; Participation; Latin America.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Far from constituting a neutral set of administrative mechanisms, governance defines the future of space exploration. As space activities expand and new challenges emerge – particularly in relation to the long-term sustainability of outer space – governance mechanisms increasingly determine not only how the orbital environment will be regulated, but also who participates in shaping these rules and whose interests they ultimately serve. In this context, while major spacefaring nations and even non-state actors actively shape the current parameters of space exploration, countries in the Global South often remain confined to a more limited position. Their reduced influence in space governance reflects development gaps, historical legacies of colonialism, and persistent structural inequalities that affect access to resources, technology, and decision-making forums. This structural asymmetry becomes especially concerning when sustainability is presented as a universal objective, yet the mechanisms responsible for defining its governance remain concentrated in a limited group of actors.

Any meaningful discussion on the sustainable use of outer space must therefore address the question of equity in governance. Sustainability, in this context, cannot be understood solely as an environmental or technical concern, but also as a matter of participation, representation, and norm-shaping authority within international space law structures. If sustainability is to function as more than a normative aspiration, it must be embedded in governance arrangements that enable inclusive participation and equitable influence in decision-making processes.

In this context, this article argues that addressing sustainability in space governance requires more than technical or environmental responses to emerging challenges in outer space. It requires examining how governance arrangements are structured and how decision-making processes distribute influence among different actors involved in space activities. As space governance increasingly develops through a combination of international treaties, soft law instruments, and regional initiatives, questions of participation and representation become central to understanding how the rules governing space activities are formed. While these mechanisms are often presented as neutral efforts to promote sustainability and safety in outer space, they may also reproduce geopolitical and technological asymmetries that limit the ability of Global South countries to meaningfully participate in shaping these norms.

This article adopts a doctrinal legal analysis of international space law instruments, complemented by a qualitative examination of contemporary governance initiatives and regional cooperation mechanisms involving Global South countries.

2. KEY CONCEPTS

2.1. *Global Space Governance*

Space governance refers to the system of laws, regulations, institutions, and mechanisms – both binding and non-binding – that guide and oversee space activities worldwide.² It is also the gateway to space exploration: those who control the means of governance consequently control access to resources and determine which interests will be served through space activities. For this reason, establishing global space governance has become an urgent priority, especially for guiding and coordinating efforts to solve the current need for safer and more efficient ways to conduct space activities.³ Nevertheless, only a handful of nations currently possess the capacity and influence to actively shape the future of a global space order, while Global South nations remain limited in their participation in the space sector.⁴

² Oltrogge, D. L., & Christensen, I. A. (2020). Space governance in the new space era. *Journal of Space Safety Engineering*, 7(4), 432–438. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jssse.2020.06.003>.

³ Jakhu, R. S., & Pelton, J. N. (Eds.). (2017). *Global space governance: An international study* (pp. 6–7). Springer.

⁴ Bittencourt Neto, O. de O. (2025). Emerging space faring nations: Common perspectives on space traffic management. In S. Hobe & J. Reichhold (Eds.), *Liber Amicorum Instituti Iuris Aeris, Spatialis et Cybernetici in centenarium* (Vol. 1, pp. 349–358). Carl Heymanns Verlag.

2.2. *The Global South*

For the purpose of this article, the geopolitical term “*Global South*” will refer to “underdeveloped” and “developing” countries and the challenges these nations face in participating in international space governance. The difficulties these Nations face were shaped by their collective histories of colonialism and enduring structural inequalities that continue to influence their technological and institutional capacities⁵. This concept emerged in the 1990s and, although not geographically ideal, it represents a more neutral alternative to the pejorative term “Third World”⁶ and will be used consistently throughout the text.

2.3. *Equity vs. Equality*

According to the Cambridge Dictionary, equity is defined as “the situation in which everyone is treated fairly according to their needs, and no group of people is given special treatment.”⁷ Equality, on the other hand, refers to “the right of different groups of people to have a similar social position and receive the same treatment.”⁸ Based on these definitions, it is clear that although the terms are etymologically similar, equity and equality are fundamentally distinct concepts.

This distinction has also been reflected in international environmental law. The Rio Conference,⁹ in 1992, recognized that formal equality between states is not sufficient to address global environmental challenges.¹⁰ Both frameworks recognize that effective and sustainable solutions require taking into account the different capacities, circumstances, and development levels of states.¹¹ For this reason, equity gradually emerged as an important guiding principle in the construction of international environmental governance.¹²

Within space governance, the principle of equity is essential to ensure that access to outer space is not determined solely by States’ technological or financial capacity, but by a fair regime that considers the needs and participation rights of all. It is particularly important for preventing the exhaustion of finite orbital resources and for recognizing that countries which have contributed most to space pollution bear greater responsibility for its mitigation.¹³

In addition, particularly in the context of the long-term sustainability of space activities, it is worth emphasizing that equity must be considered not only by the nations of today but also in relation to future generations, ensuring that outer space remains accessible and beneficial for all.¹⁴

⁵ Jakhu, R. S., & Pelton, J. N., *supra note 2* at 567.

⁶ West-Pavlov, R. (2018). *Toward the Global South*. In R. West-Pavlov (Ed.), *The Global South and Literature* (pp. 4–10). Cambridge University Press.

⁷ Cambridge University Press & Assessment. (n.d.). *Equity*. In *Cambridge Dictionary* <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/us/dictionary/english/equity>.

⁸ Cambridge University Press & Assessment. (n.d.). *Equality*. In *Cambridge Dictionary* <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/us/dictionary/english/equality>.

⁹ United Nations. (1992). *Rio Declaration on Environment and Development*. In *Report of the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development* (U.N. Doc. A/CONF.151/26/Rev.1 (Vol. I)). [https://undocs.org/en/A/CONF.151/26/Rev.1\(vol.I\)](https://undocs.org/en/A/CONF.151/26/Rev.1(vol.I)).

¹⁰ Louka, E. (2006). *International environmental law: Fairness, effectiveness, and world order*. (p 38). Cambridge University Press.

¹¹ *Ibid.*

¹² Rajamani, L. (2003). From Stockholm to Johannesburg: The anatomy of dissonance in the international environmental dialogue. *European Community & International Environmental Law Review*, 12(1), 23–32.

¹³ Viikari, L. (2008). *The environmental element in space law: Assessing the present and charting the future*. (pp. 129 – 149) Brill / Martinus Nijhoff.

¹⁴ *Ibid.*, at 133-135.

3. LEGAL FOUNDATIONS OF SPACE GOVERNANCE

3.1. Legal Frameworks for Outer Space Activities

Space law primarily emerged during the 1950s, in the context of the Cold War, and provides the legal framework for establishing a fair and equitable order in outer space.¹⁵ It also aims to ensure that the benefits and progress derived from space activities are shared among all States, not only those with access to advanced technologies and substantial financial resources.¹⁶ Nearly six decades after its original drafting, the 1967 *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies (Outer Space Treaty (OST))*¹⁷ remains the cornerstone of space law, giving rise to the other four space treaties¹⁸ and the main principles guiding space exploration.

Enshrined in Article I OST, the principles of “freedom of exploration and use” and the “benefits clause” introduce the Treaty. These principles establish that the benefits of space activities must serve all countries, not only those conducting or investing in them, regardless of their level of development. By specifying “irrespective of their degree of economic or scientific development”, the Treaty promotes substantive equality, ensuring that every State is entitled to participate in and benefit from exploration, use (including commercial), and scientific investigation.¹⁹ In this way, Article I seeks to prevent any single State from monopolizing space activities, framing outer space as a shared domain where exploration and use remain a collective endeavor for the benefit of all humanity.²⁰

However, despite its inclusive aspiration, this provision primarily reflects a commitment to equality rather than equity, as is evident from its wording.²¹ Nevertheless, as presented earlier, equality does not always have the capacity to address structural disparities between States with significantly different technological, financial, and institutional capabilities, a reality that particularly affects many countries of the Global South.²² While formal equality guarantees the same legal entitlement to all States, it does not necessarily ensure that all of them possess the practical means to effectively participate in space activities and governance processes.²³

¹⁵ Martinez, P., Jankowitsch, P., Schrogl, K.-U., Di Pippo, S., & Okumura, Y. (2019). Reflections on the 50th anniversary of the Outer Space Treaty, UNISPACE+50, and prospects for the future of global space governance. *Space Policy*, 47, 28–33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2018.05.003>.

¹⁶ Monserrat Filho, J. (2009). *Direito e política na era espacial: Podemos ser mais justos no espaço do que na Terra?* [Law and politics in the space age: Can we be more just in space than on Earth?] (pp. 17). Vieira e Lentz.

¹⁷ Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies, adopted on 19 December 1966, opened for signature on 27 January 1967, entered into force on 10 October 1967.

¹⁸ *Agreement on the Rescue of Astronauts, the Return of Astronauts and the Return of Objects Launched into Outer Space*, adopted by the UN General Assembly in its resolution 2345 (XXII), opened for signature on 22 April 1968, entered into force on 3 December 1968; *Convention on International Liability for Damage Caused by Space Objects*, adopted by the UN General Assembly in its resolution 2777 (XXVI), opened for signature on 29 March 1972, entered into force on 1 September 1972; *Convention on Registration of Objects Launched into Outer Space*, adopted by the UN General Assembly in its resolution 3235 (XXIX), opened for signature on 14 January 1975, entered into force on 15 September 1976; *Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies*, adopted by the General Assembly in its resolution 34/68, opened for signature on 18 December 1979, entered into force on 11 July 1984.

¹⁹ Hobe, S., Schmidt-Tedd, K., & Schrogl, K. (Eds.). (2017). *Cologne Commentary on Space law: Outer Space Treaty* (Volynskaya, N., Katsura-Trumpel, M., & Ladeyshchikov, A., Trans., pp. 167-220). BWV Berliner Wissenschafts-Verlag.

²⁰ Bittencourt Neto, O. de O. (2025), *supra note 4*.

²¹ Article I(2) OST.

²² Rajamani, L. (2003), *supra note 12*

²³ Williams, S. M. (1975). The role of equity in the law of outer space. *International Relations*, 5(1), 776–799.

Following in the same direction, Article II of the Outer Space Treaty establishes the principle of non-appropriation, meaning that outer space is not subject to national appropriation by claim of sovereignty, use, occupation, or by any other means. This ensures that no State may claim ownership over Earth's orbits or celestial bodies, preserving outer space as a domain beyond national sovereignty.²⁴

Despite this provision, the growing and intensive use of orbital resources by current spacefaring nations raises questions as to whether the principle of non-appropriation alone is sufficient to guarantee equitable access to outer space. Although no formal appropriation occurs in the legal sense, the concentration of satellites and technological capabilities in the hands of a limited number of actors may result in a form of “*de facto* appropriation” over valuable orbital positions.²⁵ This concern becomes particularly evident in relation to the Geostationary Orbit (GEO), a physically limited orbital region whose use depends on the allocation of orbital slots and radiofrequency spectrum.²⁶

In practice, these dynamic risks restrict access for other States, particularly countries of the Global South, whose technological and financial limitations make it more difficult to secure and maintain orbital positions in increasingly congested orbital environments.²⁷

It is relevant to mention that the rules of space law apply not only to States but also to non-state actors²⁸. Pursuant to Article VI OST, States bear international responsibility for national space activities, whether they are carried out by governmental agencies or by non-governmental entities, and must ensure that national activities are conducted in conformity with the provisions of international and space law. In practice, States must exercise authorization and continuing supervision over the activities of non-governmental entities in outer space

However, although the Outer Space Treaty imposes this obligation, it does not specify the precise requirements or mechanisms through which States must implement them.²⁹ This omission leaves considerable discretion to national governments in determining how Article VI OST should be applied within their domestic legal systems.³⁰ Guided by general principles of international law and good faith, as

²⁴ Bittencourt Neto, O. de O. (2021). Outer space as a global commons and the role of space law. In K. U. Schrogl, C. Mathieu, & T. H. Chen (Eds.), *A research agenda for space policy* (pp. 1–18). Edward Elgar Publishing. DOI: [10.4337/9781800374744.00009](https://doi.org/10.4337/9781800374744.00009).

²⁵ Viikari, L. (2008), *supra note* 15 at 113.

²⁶ The Geostationary Orbit (GEO) refers to an orbital region located approximately 35,786 km above the Earth's equator where satellites move at the same rotational speed as the Earth, allowing them to appear stationary relative to a fixed point on the planet's surface. Because of its unique physical characteristics and operational requirements, the region is widely regarded as a limited orbital resource requiring international coordination. See Martha Mejia-Kaiser, *The Geostationary Ring: Practice and Law*, Studies in Space Law, Vol. 16, pp. 18 – 23 (Brill, 2020); Broadband Commission for Sustainable Development. (2018). *The state of broadband 2018: Broadband catalyzing sustainable development*. International Telecommunication Union.

²⁷ Täiäta, C. M. (2019). The future impact of the ITU regulatory framework on large constellations of satellites. In A. Froehlich (Ed.), *Legal aspects around satellite constellations* (Studies in Space Policy, Vol. 19, pp. 55–79). Springer.

²⁸ Uiederriks-Verschoor, I. H. Ph., & Kopal, V. (2008). *An introduction to space law* (p. 28). Kluwer Law International.

²⁹ Hermida, J. (2004). *Legal basis for a national space legislation* (p. 59). Kluwer Academic Publishers.

³⁰ Cheng, B. (1998). Article VI of the 1967 Space Treaty revisited: “International responsibility,” “national activities,” and “the appropriate state.” *Journal of Space Law*, 26(1), 7–32.

reflected in the *Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties*,³¹ States are therefore expected to develop effective legal and regulatory mechanisms to ensure compliance with their international obligations.³²

This regulatory flexibility is particularly relevant for the long-term sustainability of space activities. As private actors increasingly participate in space operations, effective national authorization and supervision mechanisms are essential to ensure responsible conduct and to protect the orbital environment.³³ However, States differ significantly in their ability to develop and implement such regulatory frameworks, as many countries of the Global South are still building the institutional and legal capacities needed to engage more actively in space activities.³⁴

While the foundational principles established by the Outer Space Treaty continue to guide space activities and have played a crucial role in shaping national space law systems, technological advances and the rapid expansion of the sector have introduced challenges that were not fully anticipated when the Treaty was drafted.³⁵ These developments have prompted the emergence of additional governance mechanisms, raising broader questions about equitable participation in the regulation and use of outer space.

3.2. *Soft Law and Sustainability*

The 1992 Rio Conference, as mentioned above, represents a key milestone in the development of international environmental law. Earlier, the 1972 Stockholm Conference³⁶ had already marked a turning point by raising global awareness of the importance of integrating sustainability into development policies. These developments reflected an increasing recognition that human activities could produce long-term environmental consequences and therefore required coordinated governance mechanisms capable of addressing them.³⁷

When the Outer Space Treaty was drafted in 1967, the possibility that decades of continuous launches would result in ultimate problems was not fully anticipated. However, the rapid expansion of space activities and technological advances over the past decades has raised increasing concerns about the sustainability of the orbital environment.³⁸ These challenges include the growing accumulation of space debris, the congestion of valuable orbital regions, the expansion of large satellite constellations, and the

³¹According to Article 11 of the *Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties* (adopted on 22 May 1969, opened for signature on 23 May 1969 by the United Nations Conference on the Law of Treaties and Entry into force 27 January 1980), States may express their consent to be bound by a treaty through “signature, exchange of instruments constituting the treaty, ratification, acceptance, approval, accession, or by any other means agreed upon.” Furthermore, pursuant to Article 26 of the same Convention, “Every treaty in force is binding upon the parties to it and must be performed by them in good faith.” In other words, States that express their consent to be bound by a treaty are required to comply with it in accordance with the international law principle of *pacta sunt servanda*; Cheng, B. (1987). *General principles of law as applied by international courts and tribunals* (p. 112). Grotius Publications.

³² Von der Dunk, F. (1992). Liability versus responsibility in space law: Misconception or misconstruction. In *Proceedings of the 34th Colloquium on the Law of Outer Space* (p. 363).

³³ Marboe, I. (2015). National space law. In F. von der Dunk & F. Tronchetti (Eds.), *Handbook of space law* (pp. 133 - 135). Edward Elgar Publishing.

³⁴ Diederiks-Verschoor, I. H. Ph., & Kopal, V. (2008). *An introduction to space law* (3rd ed., pp. 80 - 81). Kluwer Law International.

³⁵ Steer, C. (2017). Sources and law-making processes relating to space activities. In R. S. Jakhu & P. S. Dempsey (Eds.), *Routledge handbook of space law* (pp. 3 - 24). Routledge.

³⁶ United Nations. (1972). Declaration of the United Nations Conference on the Human Environment. In Report of the United Nations Conference on the Human Environment (U.N. Doc. A/CONF.48/14/Rev.1). <https://undocs.org/en/A/CONF.48/14/Rev.1>.

³⁷ Sands, P., & Peel, J. (2012). *Principles of international environmental law* (3rd ed., pp. 22 - 40). Cambridge University Press.

³⁸ Martinez, P., Jankowitsch, P., Schrogl, K.-U., Di Pippo, S., & Okumura, Y. (2019), *supra note 14*.

need for more effective space traffic management. Some of these developments have the potential to disrupt, and in extreme cases even halt, space activities.³⁹

In response, discussions within the United Nations Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (UNCOPUOS), particularly since the 2010s, have sought to address these challenges. Beyond the existing hard law framework, the *UNCOPUOS Guidelines for the Long-Term Sustainability of Outer Space Activities* (LTS Guidelines), adopted in 2019, represent an important soft law initiative.⁴⁰ The set of twenty-one voluntary guidelines aims to promote responsible behavior, international cooperation, and the safe and sustainable use of outer space by encouraging the adoption of internationally recognized practices intended to mitigate risks to space operations and the orbital environment.⁴¹

Despite their non-binding nature, these soft-law instruments play a crucial role in coordinating the interests of both States and private actors and in adapting governance mechanisms to the rapidly evolving space environment. Their flexibility allows for the development of guidelines and best practices that reflect the interests of different stakeholders while encouraging cooperation and responsible conduct.⁴² Nevertheless, the implementation of non-binding sustainability-oriented instruments also raises broader questions of equity, particularly regarding inclusion and the capacity of different States to participate in shaping and applying these norms.

4. STRUCTURAL CHALLENGES AND INEQUALITIES AFFECTING THE GLOBAL SOUTH

4.1. Geopolitical Asymmetries in Global Space Governance

Between hard and soft law, space governance regulates activities at the national, regional, and international levels. Nevertheless, current geopolitical tensions and the rise of regional blocs have limited the effectiveness of truly multilateral cooperation. As a result, powerful spacefaring nations, such as the United States, China, and members of the European Union, largely define the rules for future space exploration, and the Global South participates in this discussion without significantly influencing the agenda or shaping norms.⁴³

In theory, this contradicts Article I OST, which, as noted above, mandates that the exploration and use of outer space should be conducted for the benefit and in the interest of all countries, regardless of their economic or scientific development, thereby affirming the nature of space as the “province of all mankind”. Yet even though the advancement of space exploration and the safety of these activities are interests shared by all humanity and should be discussed considering the needs of all States, the reality of governance is far from equal.

In 2014, during the *Second Manfred Lachs International Conference on Global Space Governance* held at the McGill Institute of Air & Space Law, representatives from 22 countries, including spacefaring and non-spacefaring nations, gathered to adopt the *Montreal Declaration on Global Space Governance*. Subsequently, in 2017, McGill University conducted the *Global Space Governance Study*,⁴⁴ resulting in

³⁹ Oltrogge, D. L., & Christensen, I. A. (2020), *supra note 2*.

⁴⁰ Martinez, P. (2021). The UN COPUOS guidelines for the long-term sustainability of outer space activities. *Journal of Space Safety Engineering*, 8(2), 98–107. DOI: [10.1016/j.jsse.2021.02.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsse.2021.02.003).

⁴¹ *Ibid.*

⁴² Aoki, S. (2012). The function of “soft law” in the development of international space law. In I. Marboe (Ed.), *Soft law in outer space: The function of non-binding norms in international space law* (pp. 57–87). Böhlau Verlag.

⁴³ Jakhu, R. S., & Pelton, J. N., *supra note 2* at 592.

⁴⁴ *Idem* (2017). *Global space governance: Key proposed actions [Executive summary]*. Institute of Air and Space Law, McGill University. https://www.mcgill.ca/iasl/files/iasl/global_space_governance_-_executive_summary_and_key_proposed_actions.pdf

an executive summary presenting the strengths and weaknesses of different countries and regions in implementing global space governance.

The study reinforces the argument that, despite the significant capabilities of some States, many countries, particularly in the Global South, continue to face structural barriers that limit their effective participation in global space governance.⁴⁵ While regions such as Europe benefit from strong institutional frameworks and coordinated governance mechanisms,⁴⁶ many Global South countries lack even basic structures for cooperation. Structural challenges such as limited budgets, technological gaps, and political and economic constraints continue to restrict their ability to participate more actively in shaping space governance.⁴⁷

4.2. *Structural and Institutional Barriers to Space Development*

As mentioned above, numerous factors prevent the Global South from actively shaping the future of space exploration, consequently delaying the development of global space governance. Moreover, these countries rely heavily on more developed nations to conduct space exploration,⁴⁸ reflected in their dependence on foreign launch services, access to advanced technologies, and restricted participation in international missions.

A well-established spacefaring nation may experiment in the space sector, investing time and money in research activities and newer space technology. It is also in their interest that the future of space activities remains safe for exploration and exploitation.⁴⁹ For these reasons, creating soft law mechanisms and guidelines to mitigate the effects of excessive orbital traffic and space debris is high up on these States' agenda, as the preservation and sustainability of space activities have emerged as key priorities for these countries.⁵⁰ However, as established in the topic above, for Global South nations, there remain more pressing issues demanding attention.

This does not mean that sustainability challenges in outer space will remain unaddressed, but rather that their resolution may occur without the effective participation of Global South nations.⁵¹ Consequently, in the absence of their involvement, there is no guarantee that the future of space exploration will accommodate their long-term needs and priorities.

5. PATHWAYS TOWARD INCLUSIVE AND SUSTAINABLE SPACE GOVERNANCE

5.1. *Straightening regional cooperation*

Given that countries in the Global South may not be able to prioritize space-related matters exclusively, how can they effectively engage in the future of space exploration? Although the solution is complex, it largely depends on strengthening cooperative mechanisms that allow Global South countries to collectively develop technological capacity and increase their influence in global space governance processes. One nation alone may not have the financial and technical resources to explore space, but regional strategies can overcome these limitations. Considering this, the following sections (5.2, 5.3 and 5.4) highlight a few regional initiatives promoted by the Global South to advance space exploration.

⁴⁵ *Ibid.* at 8.

⁴⁶ *Ibid.*

⁴⁷ *Ibid.*

⁴⁸ Dolman, E. C. (2002). *Astropolitik: Classical geopolitics in the space age* (p. 154). Frank Cass Publishers.

⁴⁹ Bittencourt Neto, O. de O. (2021), *supra note* 23.

⁵⁰ Aoki, S. (2012), *supra note* 9 at 62 – 63.

⁵¹ Hafner, G. (2012). The Declaration on International Cooperation in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space for the Benefit and in the Interest of All States. In I. Marboe *supra note* 9 at 267–287.

5.2. Latin America

In the case of Latin America, due to its location near the Equator, the region holds significant strategic potential in the space sector⁵² but continues to face persistent structural challenges, including limited financial and technological resources, underdeveloped space infrastructure, and a regional integration process that remains in its early stages.⁵³ Regional integration for the joint use of space resources remains limited, and there is a notable absence of robust public policies addressing the technological and financial challenges inherent to the development and management of space activities.⁵⁴ However, there are a few initiatives that promote cooperation among Latin American countries, such as the SABIA-Mar satellite, a joint Argentina-Brazil mission for ocean and coastal observation,⁵⁵ and the Latin American and Caribbean Space Agency (ALCE), based in Mexico, which promotes regional cooperation in space technology, satellite applications, and environmental monitoring.⁵⁶

Beyond these institutional initiatives, regional cooperation in Latin America has also been shaped by structural constraints faced by emerging spacefaring nations. Countries in the region often rely on a limited number of space assets, making secure and sustainable access to satellite services particularly important for economic development and environmental monitoring.⁵⁷ At the same time, budgetary limitations and restricted access to strategic technologies have historically constrained the development of autonomous space capabilities. As a result, regional and international cooperation has increasingly been viewed as a strategic pathway to strengthen technological capacity and enhance Latin American participation in global discussions on the governance and sustainability of outer space.⁵⁸

While initiatives like ALCE represent important first steps, the absence of key countries, such as Brazil, highlights ongoing challenges to full regional integration. This limitation illustrates the broader structural challenge faced by many Global South regions, where fragmented institutional frameworks continue to hinder coordinated participation in international space governance processes.

⁵² Locations close to the equator provide important advantages for rocket launches. The higher rotational speed of the Earth's surface at these latitudes reduces the energy required to place a spacecraft into orbit, which lowers fuel consumption and operational costs. In addition, such regions often offer favorable conditions for launch operations, including lower air traffic density and access to a wider range of orbital inclinations. See Brazilian Air Force. (2025, December). *Brazil prepares first commercial rocket launch from the Alcântara Launch Center*. <https://www.fab.mil.br/notimp/mostra/15122025>.

⁵³ Barrene Irigoien, J. (1984). *International space law and international cooperation* [El derecho internacional del espacio y la cooperación internacional]. *Revista Chilena de Derecho*, 11(2–3), 543–552.

⁵⁴ Barrene Irigoien, J. (1984). El derecho internacional del espacio y la cooperación internacional [International space law and international cooperation]. *Revista Chilena de Derecho*, 11(2–3), 543–552.

⁵⁵ Agência Espacial Brasileira. (2023). *AEB e INPE participam da MCDR do satélite SABIA-Mar argentino* [AEB and INPE participate in the MCDR of the Argentine SABIA-Mar satellite]. <https://www.gov.br/inpe/pt-br/assuntos/ultimas-noticias/inpe-e-aeb-participam-da-mcdr-do-satelite-sabia-mar-argentino>; Comisión Nacional de Actividades Espaciales (CONAE). (n.d.). *Misiones Espaciales: SABIA-Mar* [Space Missions: SABIA-Mar]. <https://www.argentina.gob.ar/ciencia/conae/misiones-espaciales/sabia-mar>.

⁵⁶ México. Secretaría de Relaciones Exteriores. (2021). *Latin American and Caribbean Space Agency Charter enters into force*. <https://www.gob.mx/sre/prensa/latin-american-and-caribbean-space-agency-charter-enters-into-force?idiom=en>;

México. (2024, June). *Technical presentation: Latin American and Caribbean Space Agency (ALCE)*. Presented at the 61st session of the Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space, Vienna: UNOOSA. https://www.unoosa.org/documents/pdf/copuos/2024/Technical_Presentations/24AM/3_Item_5_-_Technical_Presentation_Mexico_-_Final_Version_1.pdf.

⁵⁷ Bittencourt Neto, O. de O., & Becerra, J. (2024). Space security from Latin American perspectives. In S. M. Pekkanen & P. J. Blount (Eds.), *The Oxford handbook of space security* (pp. 475–494). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780197582671.013.26>.

⁵⁸ *Ibid.*

Drawing on international experience, coordinated adoption of sustainability guidelines, such as the *European Code of Conduct for Space Debris Mitigation*, demonstrates how technical recommendations can be operationalized, a model ALCE could follow to avoid Latin America being left behind in orbital sustainability governance.⁵⁹

Complementing these efforts, the *Buenos Aires Declaration on Cooperation in Space Law* emphasizes the need for joint programs in priority areas like remote sensing and space meteorology, the strengthening of space law as an academic and policy tool, and the creation of binational initiatives linking research, technical training, and public policy.⁶⁰

5.3. Asia and the Pacific

The Asia-Pacific Space Cooperation Organization (APSCO), established in 2008 and headquartered in Beijing, represents one of the most prominent examples of regional space governance initiatives involving Asian states. As an intergovernmental organization, APSCO provides an institutional framework through which member countries can cooperate in the peaceful use of outer space, particularly through joint projects, data sharing, and capacity-building programs in space science, technology, and applications. Its Member States include Bangladesh, China, Iran, Mongolia, Pakistan, Peru, Thailand, and Turkey, reflecting an effort to promote South–South cooperation in the development and use of space technologies.⁶¹

Although it represents an important initiative of South-South cooperation, APSCO still faces challenges, as it does not encompass most Asian countries and remains limited by disparities in technical and financial capacities among its members, dependence on China for infrastructure and resources, and the need to strengthen regional integration and autonomy in space governance.⁶²

Beyond its institutional structure, APSCO also illustrates how regional organizations may contribute to broader discussions on the long-term sustainability of outer space activities. Because many of its member states are emerging space actors with limited independent capabilities, cooperation within APSCO functions not only as a mechanism for technology sharing but also as a platform for capacity building and coordinated policy development. In this context, regional organizations can complement global governance efforts by promoting shared standards, exchanging technical knowledge, and facilitating the implementation of sustainability-related practices, such as debris mitigation and space traffic coordination.⁶³ Such initiatives demonstrate how regional cooperation can strengthen participation of developing states in the governance of outer space while simultaneously supporting the broader objective of maintaining the long-term sustainability of space activities.

5.4. Africa

The African Space Agency (AfSA), established in 2025 and headquartered in Egypt’s Space City, Cairo, functions as the continental body of the African Union tasked with coordinating and implementing space-related activities across Africa. Its mission is to foster cooperation among African nations and with international partners, advancing the use of space science and technology to support the region’s development objectives.⁶⁴

⁵⁹ Mejía-Kaiser, M. (2009). Informal regulations and practices in the field of space debris mitigation. *Annals of Air and Space Law*, 34(1), 21–34.

⁶⁰ Monserrat Filho, J., *supra* note 4 at 164 - 165.

⁶¹ Asia-Pacific Space Cooperation Organization. (2018). What is APSCO? <http://www.apSCO.int/html/comp1/content/WhatisAPSCO/2018-06-06/33-144-1.shtml>.

⁶² Jakhu, R. S., & Pelton, J. N., *supra* note 2 at 73 – 80.

⁶³ Yan, Y. (2019). Maintaining long-term sustainability of outer space activities: Creation of regulatory framework to guide Asia-Pacific Space Cooperation Organization and selected legal issues. *Space Policy*, 47, 40–48. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2018.06.002>.

⁶⁴ African Space Agency. (n.d.). *Our history*. <https://africanspaceagency.org/our-history/>.

Despite regional challenges, AfSA stands out for bringing together a wide range of African countries. Although it is still too early to assess its long-term development, the agency already represents an important step toward strengthening regional cooperation and coordinated space governance on the continent. While initiatives such as AfSA strengthen regional coordination, they also reflect a broader dynamic within the development of international space law. From its early stages, the legal framework governing outer space has emphasized the need to balance the interests of different states and to ensure that space activities are carried out for the benefit of the international community guided by principles of justice and equity.⁶⁵

In this context, regional cooperation mechanisms can play an important role in enabling states to coordinate interests, develop capabilities, and collectively participate in broader international governance structures.⁶⁶ By fostering coordination, knowledge exchange, and institutional development, regional organizations such as AfSA contribute to reducing structural asymmetries and enabling a more balanced participation of different regions in international space governance.

5.5. *Capacity Building, Knowledge Production, and Legal Empowerment in the Global South*

As mentioned before, cooperation alone will not address all governance challenges. Governments and high-level representatives undoubtedly play a decisive role in shaping the legal and political frameworks of space activities. However, the concern lies with the future of space exploration, and, in this case, it is equally necessary to invest in the generations who will one day occupy these positions of leadership and decision-making.⁶⁷

The most effective way to achieve this is through education and capacity building. By sharing expertise, infrastructure, and research capabilities across countries, particularly between developed space-faring nations and emerging space-faring nations in the Global South, technological cooperation ensures that all actors can participate meaningfully in space exploration.⁶⁸ Not only that, but education should also be a priority.

Space law, although not new, is not widely understood or accessible, particularly in the Global South. Strengthening knowledge in this field ensures that States and private actors can participate effectively in international space governance, comply with legal obligations, and contribute to the sustainable and peaceful exploration of outer space. Educational programs, workshops, moot courts, and specialized courses are essential tools to promote knowledge, local expertise, and foster collaboration across borders.⁶⁹

In this context, initiatives that promote the internationalization of young professionals from the Global South, such as scholarships, research fellowships, and technical exchange programs, are essential to empower new voices and foster more inclusive perspectives in space governance. Diversity in academic and professional backgrounds is widely recognized as enriching the debate and enabling more innovative and equitable approaches to global challenges. Universities, international organizations, and national governments should therefore collaborate to expand educational and research opportunities in space law and policy.⁷⁰

⁶⁵ Froehlich, A., Ringas, N., & Wilson, J. (2020). A look at governance throughout Africa. In A. Froehlich (Ed.), *Space supporting Africa, volume 3: Security, peace, and development through efficient governance supported by space applications* (pp. 1–51). Springer.

⁶⁶ Jakhu, R. S., & Pelton, J. N. (2017), *supra* note 3.

⁶⁷ Cheng, B. (1979). *Manual on space law* (p. 274). Oceana Publications.

⁶⁸ Hafner, G. (2012), *supra* note 48.

⁶⁹ Von Der Dunk, F. (2003). Overview of educational programmes in space law. In *Proceedings of the UN/IASL Workshop on Capacity Building. Office for Outer Space Affairs, United Nations Office* (Session 3, p. 431).

⁷⁰ Ciro Arévalo Yepes (2003). Application of Space Science and Technology in the Americas and its Benefits for Civil Society, In *supra* note 30 at 517 – 524.

Several international initiatives already seek to advance these capacity-building objectives. For instance, the United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs (UNOOSA), in cooperation with Luxembourg, launched the Space Law for New Space Actors⁷¹ initiative to support emerging spacefaring nations in developing national legal frameworks and strengthening institutional expertise in space governance. Similarly, the Global Space Law Project⁷² promotes training programs and technical assistance aimed at expanding legal knowledge in space law among developing countries. Additional initiatives, such as the Access to Space for All program and the United Nations–affiliated Regional Centers for Space Science and Technology Education,⁷³ provide training opportunities and institutional support for students and professionals from emerging space nations.

Academic initiatives also play an important role in this context, particularly the Manfred Lachs Space Law Moot Court Competition,⁷⁴ organized by the International Institute of Space Law, which has contributed to training new generations of space law practitioners and scholars from different regions of the world.

Encouraging young scientists, lawyers, and policymakers from the Global South to participate in international congresses, training programs, and professional networks, therefore, represents an important step toward strengthening their presence in global space governance discussions. By expanding opportunities for education, cooperation, and institutional development, capacity-building initiatives can help reduce structural inequalities in participation and contribute to a more inclusive and sustainable framework for the governance of outer space.

6. CONCLUSION

The growing intensity of space activities has renewed attention to the governance structures that regulate the use of outer space. As this article has demonstrated, the current legal and institutional framework, composed of foundational treaties, soft law instruments, and emerging cooperative initiatives, plays a decisive role in shaping how space activities are organized and regulated. While these mechanisms have established an important normative remark for the peaceful use of outer space, they have developed within a geopolitical environment marked by disparities in technological capacity, financial resources, and institutional influence among states.

Within this context, equity becomes central to understanding the limits of existing governance arrangements. Although international space law formally guarantees equal rights to explore and use outer space, the principle of equality alone is insufficient to address the structural differences that shape states' actual ability to participate in space activities and governance processes. As a result, countries with greater technological and economic capabilities continue to exert disproportionate influence, while many nations of the Global South remain constrained by limited resources and institutional capacity.

The analysis presented throughout this article also highlights the role of cooperative mechanisms as pathways for expanding participation and strengthening institutional capacity. Regional initiatives, joint

⁷¹ United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. (2024). *Space law for new space actors project: UN/UNU regional space law technical advisory mission for Asia and the Pacific countries (APTAM24)*. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/capacitybuilding/advisory-services/aptam24.html>.

⁷² United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. (n.d.). *Global space law project: Legal advisory services and capacity-building activities*. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/spacelaw/capacitybuilding/advisory-services/summary-of-the-project.html>.

⁷³ United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs. (n.d.). *Regional centres for space science and technology education affiliated to the United Nations*. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/psa/regional-centres/index.html>.

⁷⁴ International Institute of Space Law. (n.d.). *About the Manfred Lachs space law moot court competition*. <https://iisl.space/about-the-manfred-lachs-space-law-moot-court-competition/>.

missions, and educational programs contribute to the development of technical expertise, legal knowledge, and policy coordination among emerging space actors. By fostering cooperation and knowledge exchange, these initiatives help create conditions for broader engagement in the governance of outer space.

Ultimately, the long-term sustainability of space activities will depend not only on technical standards and regulatory instruments but also on the inclusiveness of the governance structures through which these rules are developed. Advancing a more equitable approach to space governance is therefore not only a matter of fairness but also a necessary condition for enabling broader participation, particularly from countries of the Global South, in shaping the legal and institutional framework governing outer space. Such participation is essential to ensure that the long-term sustainability of space activities reflects the interests and needs of the international community today and in the future.